

Understanding of Hypertension & Their Management through Ayurveda - A Review

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is a major cause of premature death. Hypertension is also called 'silent killer'. Silent because it doesn't produce any significant symptoms and killer because hypertension can increase the risk of heart disease, kidney failure and other disorder if hypertension is neglected and remains untreated. Hypertension is elevated pressure of blood in arteries. The increase in blood pressure depends upon a person's age, sex, physical and mental activities, family history and diet. Normal blood pressure in a healthy adult age 18 is 120 mmHg systolic and 80 mmHg diastolic. Hypertension in adult age 18 years and older is defined as systolic blood pressure of 140 mmHg or more and diastolic blood pressure of 90 mmHg or more or any level of blood pressure in taking antihypertensive medication. In Ayurveda acharya yadunandan Upadhyay has equated the term raktagata Vata for hypertension. In raktagata vata raktadhatu gets contaminated by vitiated vata and leading to shoshan of rakta dhatu. Therefore raktadhatu is unable to carry out its normal function of jeevan, varnaprasadan, mamsa poshan etc. In modern science some effective treatments are available but these are having their own complication. In ayurveda we found herbal drugs and herbomineral preparations have not any complication and side effect. We can use these drugs safely and effectively. The concept of treatment of raktagata vata reduces the quantitative increase of raktadhatu and also normalize the gati of vata dosha.

ABSTRACT

Now a day's hypertension is the commonest disease. Every fifth person is found hypertensive. According to the world health statistics report in India 23.10 percent men and 22.6 percent women above 25 years suffer from hypertension. In every year unwholesome diet and sedentary lifestyle increasing patient of high blood pressure. Hypertension is a major risk factor for stroke, myocardial infarction, vascular disease and chronic kidney disease. Hypertension is defined as systolic blood pressure of 140 mmHg or more, or diastolic blood pressure of 90 mmHg or more or taking antihypertensive medication. In the ayurvedic text, there is no clear description of hypertension. Ayurvedacharya yadunandan upadhyay has compared hypertension with raktagata vata. The disease raktagata vata is mentioned under the context of vatavyadhi. It is consider as tridoshaja vyadhi. Modern medicines have many adverse effect and damage many organs. Therefore we need safe and effective medicine in present era. We can control hypertension and balance three doshas safely and effectively through ayurvedic drugs and pathya sevan.

KEYWORDS: Hypertension, Raktagatavat, Pathya ahara

Blood pressure:-

Definition - lateral pressure exerted by the blood on the vessel walls while flowing through it.

Hypertension:-

Definition - High blood pressure is a trait as opposed to a specific disease and represents a quantitative rather than a qualitative deviation from the harm.

Criteria for classification of blood pressure :-

Normal-	Systolic < 120 mmHg Dystolic < 80 mmHg
Prehypertension -	Systolic 120-139mmHg Diastolic 80-89mmHg
Stage1-	Systolic 140-159mmHg Diastolic 90-99mmHg
Stage2 -	Systolic 160mmHg or greater Diastolic 100mmHg or greater

Classification:-

1. Primary or essential hypertension
2. Secondary hypertension

Cause :-

Primary hypertension -

1. Environmental factors
2. Genetic factors

Secondary hypertension -

1. Renal -
 - A. Acute nephritis
 - B. Interstitial nephritis and pyelonephritis
 - C. Polycystic kidneys
 - D. Renal artery stenosis
 - E. Diabetic nephropathy
2. Endocrine-
 - A. Pheochromocytoma
 - B. Thyrotoxicosis
 - C. Cushing's syndrome
 - D. Myxedema
3. Exogenous - administration of steroids, nonsteroidal, anti-inflammatory drugs
4. Neurological -
 - A. Raised intracranial tension
 - B. lead encephalopathy
5. Pregnancy induced hypertension
6. Cardiovascular hypertension -
 - A. Coarctation of aorta
 - B. Aortic regurgitation
7. Drugs and Toxins - Glucocorticoids, sibutramine, alcohol, cocaine etc.
8. Miscellaneous -
 - A. Polycythemia
 - B. Obstructive sleep apnea
 - C. Hypercalcemia

Symptoms -: The clinical feature may be due to -

1. Elevated blood pressure itself
2. Target organ involvement
3. Underlying disease as in secondary hypertension

1. Due to hypertension -:

- A. Headache
- B. Dizziness
- C. Epitasis

2. Due to the affection of target organs -:

- I. CVS -
 - A. Dyspnoea
 - B. Anginal chest pain
 - C. Palpitation
- II. Kidneys - Hematuria, Nocturia, Polyuria
- III. CNS - Transient ischemic attacks with focal neurological deficit
 - A. Hypertensive encephalopathy
 - B. Dizziness, tinnitus, and syncope
- IV. Retina - Blurred vision or sudden blindness

In Ayurved clinical feature of raktagata vata -:

- | | |
|--------------------|---|
| Teevra ruja | - Acute pain |
| Santap | - Burning sensation |
| Vaivarnya | - Discoloration of skin |
| Krushata | - Emaciation |
| Aruchi | - Anorexia |
| Arumsi | - Appearance of rashes on the body |
| Bhuktashya stambha | - Stiffness of the body after taking food |

Samprapti - :

Risk factors -:

- Common in blacks
- Prevalence increase with age
- Obesity
- Alcohol
- Stress
- Drugs
- Smoking
- Dyslipidemia
- Diabetes mellitus
- High sodium intake
- Physical inactivity
- Family history of premature CAD

The complication of hypertension -:

1. CNS -
 - A. Transient ischaemic attacks
 - B. Cerebrovascular accidents
 - C. Subarachnoid hemorrhage
 - D. Hypertensive encephalopathy
2. Ophthalmic - hypertensive retinopathy
3. Cardiovascular -
 - A. coronary artery disease
 - B. Left ventricular failure
 - C. Aortic aneurism
 - D. Aortic dissection
4. Renal -
 - A. Proteinuria
 - B. Progressive renal failure

Investigation -:

1. 24-hour ambulatory blood pressure monitoring
2. Urine analysis for protein, blood, and glucose
3. Renal function test
4. Serum electrolytes
5. FBS & PPBS
6. Serum cholesterol and triglycerides
7. Serum calcium and uric acid
8. ECG
9. Chest radiograph

Treatment -:

- **Nidana parivarjana** Avoidance of causative factors
- **Sheeta pradaha** Coolant ointment
- **Vireka** Purgation

- **Raktamokshana** Bloodletting therapies
- **Basti** Enema decoction
- **Sirodhara**
- **As a vasodilator** Arjuna, garlic etc and their preparation like Arjuna churna, arjunarista
- **As a diuretics** Arjuna, punarnava, gokshura etc and their Preparation like gokshura powder, punarnavashava
- **As a stress reduction** Jatamansi, shnkhpushpi, bramhi etc and their Preparation like saraswat powder saraswatarishta & yoga, pranayam
- We can use also some **herbomineral preparation** like hridayanava rasa, tarkeshwar rasa, praval pishti etc.

PATHYA/APATHYA :-

1. Avoid meat, eggs, salt, pickles, tea and coffee
2. Regular exercise at least 30 minutes daily
3. Avoid alcohol and smoking
4. Reduce intake of dietary saturated fat and cholesterol
5. Increase the use of garlic, fruit, and green vegetables
6. Laughter is the best medicine as it relieves stress and anxiety which are the main cause of high blood pressure in the present era.

Conclusion :-

Hypertension is a worldwide problem and a major cause of mortality. The disease has primary and secondary causes. In secondary hypertension, if we treat the causative disease the blood pressure will be automatically controlled. In modern science diuretics, vasodilators, and stress reliever are used for control hypertension but due to side effect, we cannot use these medications for a long time. Thus we should be used herbal drugs and these drugs have properties of diuretics, vasodilators and stress relievers.

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